

Issue:
Contemporary trends in Language Studies

We arrive at the end of 2022 with our hopes renewed. After years of struggles in order to build a university for everyone and to strengthen Science in our country, a new horizon heralds the re-establishment of perspectives of justice and equity in Brazil. The hopelessness and fear experienced in the last four years gave way to a scenario of hope and good expectations. As we breathe in these new airs, some reflections are presented here as a result of the work of several scholars in Brazil, gathered in this issue entitled *Contemporary trends in Language Studies*.

The organisers of this edition are professors Josilene Pinheiro-Mariz, from the Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG, Brazil), Maria Rennally Soares da Silva, from both the State University of Paraíba (UEPB, Brazil) and UFCG, as well as professor Alain-Philippe Durand, from the University of Arizona (United States of America).

Concerning the participating universities, we received papers from fellow professors and researchers from the following Brazilian institutions: Federal University of Fronteira Sul (UFFS), University of Brasilia (UnB), Federal University of Tocantins (UFT), Federal University of Grande Dourados (UFGD), Federal Institute of Education, Science and Technology of Amazonas (IFAM), Federal Rural University of Pernambuco (UFRPE), Federal University of Rio Grande do Norte (UFRN), Federal University of Maranhão (UFMA), Federal University of Paraíba (UFPB), Feevale University, La Salle University, Federal Rural University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRRJ), State University of Mato Grosso (UNEMAT), State University of Rio de Janeiro / Faculty of Teacher Training (UERJ/FFP), Federal University of Paraná (UFPR), Federal University of Piauí (UFPI), Federal University of Goiás (UFG), and Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG).

The first paper in this issue is ***Canción infantil y constitución del sujeto: un análisis desde la perspectiva sociointeracionista***, by Maiara Taís Zydek (UFFS) and Ana Cecilia Teixeira Gonçalves (UFFS). It analyses the process of the constitution of the subject through music, having as a corpus some parts of four children's songs, namely: *Terezinha de Jesus*, *Sambalelê*, *O Cravo e a Rosa*, and *Fui no Tororó*. The authors identify common aspects between these songs

and remark on an education focused on the reflection of ideas in an oriented manner, by leading the child to think about socially instituted aspects.

Following that, we present ***Construyendo sentidos desde el género multimodal charge: una mirada hacia la interdiscursividad***, by Alex Bezerra Leitão (UnB), Ruy Martins dos Santos Batista (UnB), and Dalve Oliveira Batista-Santos (UFT). The paper analyses how the interdiscourse permeates students' education through the activity of reading a multimodal text. Moreover, it ponders on discussions with High School students motivated by reading the multimodal genre "cartoon", published in a news media about returning to physical and presential classes amid the spread of Covid-19.

Now in the literary field of female writing, the paper ***Narrar y morder: símbolos de la violencia en Mujeres que morderm, de Beatriz Leal***, is presented by Alexandra Santos Pinheiro (UFGD) and Laura Cristina Leal e Silva (IFAM). The authors analyse the aforementioned work, by identifying the symbolism of the metaphors used by Beatriz Leal and considering the "characters who bite" in order to take control of themselves and of the world around them.

Still on Brazilian literature, we shall read the paper ***Round of hours: the train and the river as images of time in João Cabral de Melo Neto's poetry***, by Júlio César de Araújo Cadó (UFRN) and Rosanne Bezerra de Araújo (UFRN). It analyses the figuration of time in the poetry of João Cabral de Melo Neto and identifies the representation of the river and the train as paradigmatic images intertwined in his poetic lines.

Por una memoria de la subversión: la condición de exilio del cuerpo travesti en "La voz de la consciencia", de Atena Beauvoir, by Maria Isabela Berenguer de Menezes (UFRPE), Brenda Carlos de Andrade (UFRPE), and Natanael Duarte de Azevedo (UFRPE) is the following paper. The authors discuss the representation of the transvestite body in literature, by analysing some aspects of the aforementioned story from the book "*Contos Transantropologistas*", by Atena Beauvoir. The text presents some notions of inclusion and plurality on literature, the body, the discourse and society, besides identifying the condition of exile in the transvestite character in the short story analysed.

Afterwards, ***The between worlds of dreams and oppression in the novel 'Marginais', by Evel Rocha***, is the paper written by Aldenora Márcia Chaves Márcia Pinheiro-Carvalho, from the Federal University of Maranhão (UFMA) and doctoral candidate at the Federal University of Campina Grande (UFCG), Maria Marta Santos Silva Nóbrega (UFCG), and Ana Paula Araújo

Barbosa (UFPB). The authors present a decolonial reading of the novel studied; a representative work of contemporary Cape Verdean literature. The investigation shows the intertwined historical and social context resulting from post-colonialism in Cape Verde and the consequent social and institutional relations that were established when the new Cape Verdean social structures were reorganised and consolidated.

Not moving away from literary studies, the seventh concluding paper of this issue is ***Queer Africa: literature as art of resistance***, by Orison Marden Bandeira de Melo Junior (UFRN) and Vanessa Neves Riambau Pinheiro (UFPB). The text discusses the context of criminalisation of homosexuality in the countries of birth of the authors of the short stories from the collections “Queer Africa: New and Collected Fiction” and “Queer Africa 2: New Stories”. Thereby, they demonstrate how the writers brought to the fictional world the representation of conflicts experienced by characters who discover or experience their sexuality in homophobic or criminalising contexts.

Still in a decolonial perspective, we shall read the interview ***Saberes decoloniais latinoamericanos construídos na universidade pública brasileira: uma conversa com Livia Baptista***, carried out by José Veranildo Lopes da Costa Junior (UFPB). The professor interviewed has experience in the fields of Linguistics, Applied Linguistics, Discourse Analysis, and Education, besides working mainly on the following topics: language teaching and learning (Portuguese and Spanish), language teacher training, critical and decolonial pedagogies in Brazil and in the Latin American contexts, linguistic education, discursive practices, and translanguaging.

The second interview in this edition is ***About Dora and dores: affective encounters of women, interview with Lita Maria***, conducted by Eliane Cristina Testa (UFT) and José Pereira dos Santos Filho, from the municipal service of Palmas (Brazil). The interview features the writer Lita Maria, who occupies chair nº 19 at the *Academia Palmense de Letras (APL)* [Palmas Academy of Literature]. During the conversation, some questions were mobilised addressing her poetic production and narrative works.

Following that, we present the review ***Por linhas tortas: análise de ‘Quincas Borba’, de Machado de Assis***, by Juracy Assmann Saraiva (Feevale University). It summarises the critical essay developed by Paul Dixon concerning the novel “*Quincas Borba*”, by Machado de Assis. Nonetheless, the second review ***Rinaldo de Fernandes e a inquietante escrita do mal***, by Frederico de Lima Silva (UFPB), discusses the work “*A Paixão Mortal de Paulo*”, by Rinaldo de Fernandes, a Maranhão writer situated in Paraíba (Brazil).

We conclude this edition with nine artistic productions, namely: ***Uma herança para o conhecimento***, by Idio Fridolino Altmann (La Salle University); ***Hoje não vai ter poesia***, by Joilson Bessa da Silva, from the municipal services of Campos dos Goytacazes (PMCG/SMECE/EMJP, Brazil) and Duque de Caxias (PMDC/SMEDC/EMJF, Brazil); ***Circo Pegando Fogo***, by José D'Assunção Barros (UFRRJ); ***Confissões de um boêmio na curva do Rio Paraguai***, by Adson Luan Duarte Vilasboas Seba (UNEMAT); ***Boatos***, by Bruna Machado da Rocha (UERJ/FFP); ***O recuo silencioso do mar do tsunami***, by Eliseu Raphael Venturi (UFPR); ***Petinha***, by Cleane da Silva de Lima (UFPI); ***Sementes***, by Iury Aragonez da Silva (UFG); and, last but not least, the poem ***A balsa amarela***, by Sanny Kellen Anjos Cavalcante Canuto (UNEMAT).

Dear reader, this last edition of 2022 highlights some trends in our area, as it might be identified in the several texts published here, emphasising *Contemporary trends in Language Studies*. Meanwhile, it shall instigate us to reflect on our role as teachers, professors, scholars, researchers, and students in the areas of Linguistics, Literature, and Languages. Whether in one area or another, we see a care for the natural resource that leads us through the contemporary world.

This fourth issue of this year can also be read by using the QR Code of ***Revista Letras Raras*** and features seven papers that inspire diverse reflections in the areas of Social Interactionism, Critical Discourse Analysis, Interactional Sociolinguistics, Literary Studies, and Decolonial Studies; that is, on *Contemporary trends in Language Studies*. Therefore, we come to the end of 2022 by wishing that the new Brazilian government directions evoke tolerance, respect, equity, and a focus on the investment in Education and Science. Here is our will.

We wish you all a great reading!

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